

Electrical Bioimpedance Sensing-based Proximity Distance Estimation for Needle Interventions: Two-Layer Model and Validation

Yao Zhang*, Zhuoqi Cheng*, Mouloud Ourak, Thusius Rajeeth Savarimuthu, and Emmanuel Vander Poorten

Abstract—Needle-based interventions are routine in clinical practice, yet clinicians lack reliable, precise, real-time estimates of the tip-to-target distance—a key determinant of safety and efficiency. To bridge this critical clinical gap, physics-based models that maps electrical bio-impedance (EBI) measurements to the absolute tip-to-target distance by leveraging tissue-intrinsic electrical properties encoded in EBI are presented in this work. A tripolar electrode configuration is adopted to ensure tool-independence and broad compatibility across instruments and anatomical sites. The optimal layout of electrode radius, inter-electrode spacing, and placement was identified through a systematic parametric study. The model was validated across finite-element simulations, saline solution experiments, and *ex vivo* layered tissue. In all settings, proximity distance estimates were accurate and robust across different insertion angles. In simulation, it achieved 0.55 mm RMSE/1.06 mm MAE when the target layer was less conductive than the first layer and 0.40 mm RMSE/1.21 mm MAE when it was more conductive. In saline, four insertion angles yielded millimeter errors with no angle dependence. In *ex vivo* layered tissue, accuracy remained near the millimeter level across angles (RMSE 1.00–1.13 mm and MAE 1.30–1.58 mm), which is slightly lower than saline yet consistent across orientations. Together, these results establish a general, instrument-agnostic framework for absolute proximity distance sensing during needle interventions with the potential to enhance safety and efficiency in minimally invasive procedures. Furthermore, by first focusing on a two-layer model, this work provides a clear pathway to multi-layer tissue modeling and broader anatomical generalization.

Index Terms—Electrical bioimpedance (EBI) sensing, proximity distance sensing, needle intervention, tissue characterization.

I. INTRODUCTION

NEEDLE-based interventions play a critical role in contemporary medical practice, with an estimated 16 billion such procedures performed globally each year [1]. These procedures encompass a wide range of medical scenarios, all of which could benefit by precise and accurate proximity sensing—the ability to detect the needle tip’s distance to the target tissue (Fig. 1) [2].

One common example occurs at the start of minimally invasive interventions involving femoral artery access (FAA) [3]. Here, the needle must precisely enter the lumen without

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Fig. 1. (a) Proximity sensing is widely needed across diverse medical scenarios, from initial vascular access in minimally invasive surgeries to regional medical treatment. (b) Needle-tip proximity to target tissue.

perforating the posterior arterial wall, a crucial step enabling subsequent endovascular interventions such as angiography [4], stent placement [5], and embolization [6]. Likewise, percutaneous nephrolithotomy for kidney stone removal relies on a precisely placed needle to form the first channel into the kidney [7]. Both procedures need to start with a precisely executed needle insertion that determines downstream safety and success. Biopsy procedures represent another domain, wherein needles are employed to extract small tissue specimens from suspicious lesions within the patient’s body [8]. Accurate needle placement ensures the specimen retrieved is suitable for histological diagnosis, which is essential for conditions such as lung cancer [9] and prostate cancer [10]. In addition, needle-based interventions serve therapeutic purposes, among others, anesthesia administration during eye surgery [11], lumbar spinal injections for localized pain relief with targeted drug delivery [12], and minimally invasive removal of intracranial hematoma [13]. Each therapy hinges on tip placement in the intended target without off-target penetration or breach of adjacent structures, which necessitates the precise estimation of the proximity distance sensing between the needle tip to the target layer.

To facilitate guidance during needle interventions, several

TABLE I
VARIOUS SENSING MODALITIES USED IN NEEDLE-BASED INTERVENTIONS

Modality	Principle	Limitation	Application
Ultrasound	Ultrasound	Limited resolution	Vascular cannulation [17]–[19], biopsy [15], [16]
Fluoroscopy	X-ray	Radiation exposure	Percutaneous [20], ablation [21]
MRI	Nuclear magnetic resonance	Strict material selection	Ablation [24], injection [25], biopsy [35]
OCT	Coherent interferometry	Limited tissue penetration	Alveoli tracking [27], subretinal injection [29]
EM	Magnetic field	Metal interference	Local anesthesia [33], brachytherapy [36]
Laser Doppler	Coherent laser light	Bulky dimension	Neurosurgery [34]
EBI	Electrical impedance	No absolute proximity	Vascular cannulation [37]–[40], biopsy [41]

sensing modalities are employed [14] and presented in Table. I. Ultrasound (US) offers real-time, radiation-free imaging and is widely applied in breast brachytherapy and kidney biopsy [15], [16]. However, its limited resolution and noise demand advanced processing and skilled operators [17]–[19]. X-ray fluoroscopy delivers clear guidance for tasks such as liver-tumor ablation with ~ 2.5 mm tip-tracking accuracy [20], [21], yet expose staff and patients to ionizing radiation even when robotic aids are used [22], [23]. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) overcomes radiation concerns, providing high-resolution, soft-tissue contrast for ablations and lumbar injections [24], [25], but its confined bore, strict material limits, and high costs call for specialized MRI-compatible setups [26]. Finally, optical coherence tomography (OCT) supplies micrometer-level, cross-sectional views useful in lung [27], prostate [28], and eye [29], [30], though shallow penetration depth and equipment expense currently restrict its broader clinical uptake.

Besides the widely used image-based techniques, several alternative modalities have been investigated for needle-tip proximity sensing. Electromagnetic (EM) tracking provides real-time needle pose sensing [31]. A detachable clip-on EM sensor simplifies shaft attachment [32], and fusing EM with ultrasound could improve proximity estimates while rendering the system less sensitive to metal-interference errors [33]. Nevertheless, a dedicated field generator is required, and the effective workspace is limited. Laser Doppler flowmetry—implemented intraluminally via a fiber that emits and collects coherent light from the needle lumen—can estimate vessel position for obstacle avoidance [34], yet the 4 mm-diameter optical probe increases needle bulk and limits use in narrow access paths.

Against this backdrop, electrical bio-impedance (EBI) stands out for its low cost, radiation-free operation, and straightforward integration with metallic needles. EBI’s ability to distinguish tissue types has been demonstrated in diverse biomedical applications [42]–[44] and adapted for several needle-guided interventions [39], [40]. Yet most implementations still infer depth from relative amplitude or phase changes [37] or only measuring single material [38]—signals that depend strongly on needle geometry and ignore the tissue’s intrinsic information—so absolute proximity distance remains difficult to estimate reliably.

In this work, a physics-based EBI model is proposed to

convert impedance measurements into real-time estimates of the tip-to-target distance during needle-based interventions. As the needle passes through tissue layers with distinct conductivities, the model converted EBI measurements to provide quantitative proximity feedback, enabling precise guidance along the intended path. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first demonstration of using EBI signals to estimate absolute proximity distance during needle-based interventions. The main contributions of this work can be summarized as follows:

- 1) Development of a physics-based EBI model that converts EBI signals into estimated absolute tip-to-target distance, enabling a generalizable proximity-sensing solution for needle-based interventions.
- 2) Formulation of single-layer and double-layer analytical models that provide both real-time tissue characterization and quantitative depth estimation during insertion.
- 3) Determination of optimal electrode layout through finite element (FEM) simulations and a systematic parametric study providing practical design guidelines for diverse needle-based procedures.
- 4) Experimental validation and verification in a saline phantom and in *ex vivo* tissue across multiple insertion angles, confirming the practicality and accuracy of the proposed approach.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows. Section II describes the proposed tripolar-based needle-insertion modeling. Section III details the finite-element simulation framework, the parametric study for optimal electrode placement, and the proximity-distance estimation derived from the model. Section IV describes the experimental setup and results for both saline phantoms and *ex vivo* tissue. Section V discusses the experimental results and provides some perspectives of future study. Section VI concludes this study.

II. METHODS

A. Tripolar EBI Fundamentals

In this work, a tripolar EBI configuration is adopted (Fig. 2), which strikes a practical balance between the simplicity of bipolar sensing and the stability of tetrapolar configurations. In a bipolar configuration two electrodes must alternately inject current and sense voltage, causing the measurement channel to share the excitation current and making the readings

vulnerable to drift [38]. By contrast, the tripolar arrangement employs three electrodes: a single current source electrode (A , CSE) injects the excitation signal, while the voltage measurement electrodes (VMEs) M and N independently measure local potentials. Separating excitation from sensing greatly reduces artifacts without the fourth electrode required by tetrapolar designs [45], in which current is driven between two CSEs and voltage is sensed on a separate pair of VMEs, creating a local return path and decoupling between injection and sensing. Tripolar configuration yields a slimmer, easier-to-integrate layout that streamlines clinical deployment. It maintains stable, drift-resistant EBI measurements.

Fig. 2. EBI tripolar configuration. Electrodes A : current source electrodes (CSE); electrodes M and N : voltage measurement electrodes (VMEs); equivalent sphere radius: r_0 ; current density sphere radius: r .

Figure 2 shows the tripolar arrangement with all three electrodes positioned in contact with a homogeneous tissue surface. The CSE A delivers an excitation current that spreads into an approximately hemispherical volume. The parameter r_0 denotes the equivalent radius of the active electrode immersed in tissue. Its value depends on the tool's size and shape and is generally difficult to measure or control directly. The resulting current density $J(r)$ is given in (1)

$$J(r) = \frac{i}{2\pi r^2}. \quad (1)$$

Using this density, the electric potentials at the two VMEs, M and N , are obtained in (2) and (3) based on Maxwell's equations

$$V_M = - \int_{r_0}^r J(r) dr = - \int_{r_0}^{|AM|} \frac{idr}{2\pi\sigma r^2} = \frac{i}{2\pi\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{|AM|} - \frac{1}{r_0} \right), \quad (2)$$

$$V_N = - \int_{r_0}^r J(r) dr = - \int_{r_0}^{|AN|} \frac{idr}{2\pi\sigma r^2} = \frac{i}{2\pi\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{|AN|} - \frac{1}{r_0} \right), \quad (3)$$

where σ represents the medium conductivity, and $|AM|$ and $|AN|$ denote the Euclidean distances from the source to each measurement site. Subtracting these potentials yields the inter-electrode voltage V_{MN} presented in (4)

$$V_{MN} = \frac{i}{2\pi\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{|AM|} - \frac{1}{|AN|} \right). \quad (4)$$

Notably, the term containing r_0 cancels. This makes the measured V_{MN} independent of the source-electrode geometry, which underpins the tripolar configuration's appeal. Finally, by reorganizing (4), it becomes possible to express the tissue conductivity σ as a function of the measured EBI Z_{MN} , providing the baseline for all subsequent tissue-specific models.

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{2\pi Z_{MN}} \left(\frac{1}{|AM|} - \frac{1}{|AN|} \right). \quad (5)$$

B. Insertion Model in Homogeneous Tissue

Building on the surface-based tripolar formulation of Sec. II-A, the analysis is extended in this subsection to the scenario whereby the needle is fully embedded in a single, homogeneous tissue. In the configuration under study, the needle shaft is insulated, and only the conductive tip—marked in green in Fig. 3(a) — acts as the CSE. This immersion changes the source geometry: the injected current now radiates into a full $1/4\pi$ steradian volume rather than the hemisphere considered previously in (1). The air-to-tissue boundary introduces a discontinuity to the equipotential surface and reflects part of this field back into the medium [46]. The effect of this reflection can be modeled by an image source A' located symmetrically across the interface as depicted in Fig. 3(b). The potentials at VMEs M and N has two contributions: a direct component along paths $|AM|$ and $|AN|$, and a reflected component arising from A' . These contributions yield the revised expressions in (6) and (7). The reflection coefficient k_1 is defined in (8), where σ_1 and σ_{air} represent the conductivity of the immersed tissue and the air.

Fig. 3. Insertion model in a homogeneous medium with an air-tissue interface. (a) The insulated shaft leaves only tip A as the CSE within homogeneous tissue σ_1 beneath air σ_{air} . (b) The interface reflection is modeled by an image source A' .

$$V_M = - \int_{r_0}^{|AM|} \frac{i\partial r}{4\pi\sigma r^2} - \int_{r_0}^{|A'M|} \frac{k_1 i\partial r}{4\pi\sigma r^2} = \frac{i}{4\pi\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{|AM|} + \frac{k_1}{|A'M|} - \frac{k_1 + 1}{r_0} \right), \quad (6)$$

$$V_N = - \int_{r_0}^{|AN|} \frac{i\partial r}{4\pi\sigma r^2} - \int_{r_0}^{|A'N|} \frac{k_1 i\partial r}{4\pi\sigma r^2} = \frac{i}{4\pi\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{|AN|} + \frac{k_1}{|A'N|} - \frac{k_1 + 1}{r_0} \right), \quad (7)$$

$$k_1 = \frac{\sigma_1 - \sigma_{air}}{\sigma_1 + \sigma_{air}}. \quad (8)$$

Subtracting the two potentials removes the r_0 dependence, yielding the stable measurement of voltage V_{MN} in (9).

$$V_{MN} = \frac{i}{4\pi\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{|AM|} + \frac{k_1}{|A'M|} - \frac{1}{|AN|} - \frac{k_1}{|A'N|} \right) \quad (9)$$

From this relation the tissue conductivity σ_1 can be extracted analytically in (10), using the Euclidean distances in (11), where c is the needle insertion depth, d is the distance between the needle insertion point to the VME M , and s is the inter-electrode distance between the two VMEs. The homogeneous model thus provides both a stand-alone tool for tissue characterization and the analytical baseline for the layered, nonhomogeneous formulation of Sec. II-C, where proximity to a second underlying tissue will be inferred.

$$\sigma_1 = \frac{1}{4\pi Z_{MN}} \left(\frac{1}{|AM|} + \frac{k_1}{|A'M|} - \frac{1}{|AN|} - \frac{k_1}{|A'N|} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$|AM| = |A'M| = \sqrt{d^2 + c^2} \quad |AN| = |A'N| = \sqrt{d^2 + c^2 + s^2} \quad (11)$$

C. Insertion Model in Layered Tissue

The homogeneous embedding model of Sec. II-B is generalized to a layered-tissue case where the needle approaches a deeper target layer with different conductivity. Figure 4(a) retains the tripolar setting and geometry but introduces an interface between an upper layer of conductivity σ_1 and a lower layer of conductivity σ_2 , making the medium nonhomogeneous. Two planar interfaces must therefore be considered: the air (σ_{air}) - tissue (σ_1) interface and the tissue (σ_1) - tissue (σ_2) interface at depth h .

Fig. 4. Insertion model in layered tissue. (a) Tripolar geometry with upper layer σ_1 over lower layer σ_2 at depth h . (b) Cross-section illustrating the method of reflection image points across both interfaces. Potentials at M , N sum the direct field from A and reflections from the air- σ_1 and $\sigma_1 - \sigma_2$ boundaries.

As depicted in Fig. 4(b), the potential at each VME electrode arises from four sources. Using electrode M for illustration:

- 1) *Direct term* $|AM|$: contribution from the CSE A .
- 2) *Air reflection* $|A'M|$: contribution from the image source A' mirrored across the air-tissue interface, scaled by the reflection coefficient k_1 .
- 3) *Lower-layer term* w_n : a sequence of image sources $A_{w1}, A'_{w1}, \dots, A_{wn}, A'_{wn}$ created by successive reflections between the lower (σ_1/σ_2) and upper interfaces, the index w_n denotes the n -th reflection that first strikes the lower interface.

4) *Upper-layer term* c_n : a complementary sequence $A_{c1}, A'_{c1}, \dots, A_{cn}, A'_{cn}$ that originates with an upper (σ_1/σ_{air}) interface reflection before entering the lower layer. The index c_n labels the n -th reflected image that first encounters the upper interface after reaching the lower interface.

The same four sources reach electrode N via paths $|AN|$, $|A'N|$, w'_n , and c'_n . Summing the series yields the potentials V_M and V_N in (12) and (13), where reflection k_2 is defined in (14). Notably, the coefficients in the w_n , c_n , w'_n , and c'_n involve only k_2 because those contributions exist solely due to the presence of the second layer. Subtracting V_N from V_M removes the CSE radius term r_0 , which depends on the tool configuration and difficult to measure.

$$V_M = \frac{i}{4\pi\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{|AM|} + \frac{k_1}{|A'M|} - \frac{k_1 + 1}{r_0} + 2 \sum_1^\infty \frac{k_2^n}{w_n} + 2 \sum_1^\infty \frac{k_2^n}{c_n} - 4 \sum_1^\infty \frac{k_2^n}{r_0} \right) \quad (12)$$

$$V_n = \frac{i}{4\pi\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{|AN|} + \frac{k_1}{|A'N|} - \frac{k_1 + 1}{r_0} + 2 \sum_1^\infty \frac{k_2^n}{w'_n} + 2 \sum_1^\infty \frac{k_2^n}{c'_n} - 4 \sum_1^\infty \frac{k_2^n}{r_0} \right) \quad (13)$$

$$k_2 = \frac{\sigma_1 - \sigma_2}{\sigma_1 + \sigma_2}. \quad (14)$$

Equation (15) follows by subtracting (13) from (12), i.e., $V_M - V_N$, which expresses σ_1 in terms of the measured impedance Z_{MN} and geometry. By exploiting geometric symmetry, the Euclidean distances for the paths w_n , c_n and their counterparts w'_n and c'_n are given in (16) and (17), while the direct separations $|AM|$, $|A'M|$, $|AN|$, $|A'N|$ retain the definitions in (11). The index $n = 1, 2, \dots$ labels the image-series terms, and the sums converge because k_2 described in (14) satisfies $|k_2| < 1$ for positive σ_1 and σ_2 .

$$\sigma_1 = \frac{1}{4\pi Z_{MN}} \left(\frac{1}{|AM|} + \frac{k_1}{|A'M|} + 2 \sum_{n=1}^\infty \frac{k_2^n}{w_n} + 2 \sum_{n=1}^\infty \frac{k_2^n}{c_n} - \frac{1}{|AN|} - \frac{k_1}{|A'N|} - 2 \sum_{n=1}^\infty \frac{k_2^n}{w'_n} - 2 \sum_{n=1}^\infty \frac{k_2^n}{c'_n} \right) \quad (15)$$

$$w_n = \sqrt{d^2 + (2nh - c)^2} \quad c_n = \sqrt{d^2 + (2nh + c)^2} \quad (16)$$

$$w'_n = \sqrt{(d + s)^2 + (2nh - c)^2} \quad c'_n = \sqrt{(d + s)^2 + (2nh + c)^2} \quad (17)$$

When the lower interface is pushed to far away - as the layer depth h tends to infinity - the image-series terms vanish and the expressions reduce to the single-layer homogeneous solution. This continuity check supports the correctness of the derivation. Furthermore, the series depend on both the interface depth h and the conductivity contrast between σ_1 and σ_2 . This dependence links the measured impedance Z_{MN} to depth-to-interface and tissue properties, forming the basis for absolute tip-to-target proximity sensing.

D. Proximity Estimation Formulation

Given the layered formulation in (15), three unknowns can then be solved including the layer depth h , which determines proximity to the target layer, the conductivity of the layer currently surrounding the tip σ_1 , and the lower-boundary reflection coefficient k_2 , which depends on σ_1 and σ_2 . All other quantities are known from the needle-insertion setup: the spacing s between the VMEs, the distance d from the insertion point to VME M , the insertion depth c , and the measured impedance Z_{MN} . Specifically, because air is nearly non-conductive, the reflection coefficient k_1 can be set to 1. These parameters are linked by the relationship in Eq.(18), where the triplet (h, σ_1, k_2) is estimated using a constrained, gradient-based solver `fmincon` in MATLAB (MathWorks, USA) under use-case-specific constraints. The layer depth h is bounded by the known anatomy of the clinical scenario; for example, in FAA the tissue thickness over the anterior arterial wall can be defined with [10 mm, 30 mm] [47], which can be confirmed from pre-procedure imaging. The near-field conductivity σ_1 is bounded using literature ranges for the known tissue in that scenario [48]. The reflection parameter k_2 is constrained by the (14), which implies $|k_2| < 1$.

$$f(h, \sigma_1, k_2) = \frac{1}{4\pi Z_{MN}} \left(\frac{1}{|AM|} + \frac{1}{|A'M|} + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{k_2^n}{w_n} + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{k_2^n}{c_n} - \frac{1}{|AN|} - \frac{1}{|A'N|} - 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{k_2^n}{w'_n} - 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{k_2^n}{c'_n} \right) - \sigma_1 \quad (18)$$

From the estimated parameters, the proximity distance to the target interface follows directly by subtracting the insertion depth c from the estimated layer depth h . The recovered σ_1 then provides real-time tissue characterization at the tip. In parallel, k_2 encodes the conductivity contrast to the target layer, furnishing pre-contact cues that the needle is approaching the interface. In this way, the layered model not only preserves continuity with the homogeneous limit (when the interface $\sigma_1 - \sigma_2$ is far away) but also estimates the proximity distance required for guidance in needle-based interventions.

III. SIMULATION-BASED OPTIMIZATION AND VALIDATION

In this section, the simulation-based optimization and validation of the tripolar needle-insertion model of Sec. II is presented. The optimal layout for the two surface VMEs were optimized via a parametric sweep of electrode radius and placement relative to the needle entry point. This parametric study was conducted in MATLAB's Electrical Impedance Tomography and Diffuse Optical Tomography Reconstruction Software (EIDORS) platform [49], which employs a FEM method to mesh a $500 \times 500 \times 300$ mm medium block with assigned σ_1 and σ_2 . The parameter sweep yields a optimal electrode layout that balances sensitivity, stability, and accuracy. With this layout, the feasibility of accurate proximity distance estimation for needle-based interventions was demonstrated.

A. Parametric Study: Electrode Radius

The influence of the surface VME radius on the accuracy of the tripolar needle-insertion model (Sec. II-C) was first evaluated in EIDORS. A three-layer medium (air, medium layer 1, and medium layer 2) was set up as shown in Fig. 5(a)–(b). Medium layer 1 served as the medium with ground-truth conductivity $\sigma_1 = 1$ S/m. Medium layer 2 was assigned either $\sigma_2 = 0.1$ S/m (low-conductivity) or $\sigma_2 = 10$ S/m (high-conductivity) to assess two extremes. The two circular VMEs were placed on the medium surface in the same line with the needle entry point with center-to-needle distance $s = 20$ mm and inter-electrode spacing $d = 20$ mm (Fig. 5(b)). A clinical needle was modeled as a conductive cylinder with radius 0.65 mm (BD InsyteW[®], USA), which matches the dimensions of the needle commonly used in routine FAA procedures. The thickness of layer 1 was set to 30 mm, and the insertion depth c was incremented with 1 mm step within this layer to generate the proximity trajectory.

Fig. 5. Parametric study setup for VME radius. (a) Three-layer EIDORS medium with air, first layer tissue σ_1 , and second layer tissue σ_2 . (b) Zoomed surface view showing circular VMEs M , N with inter-electrode spacing s , VME radius r , needle insertion depth c , and center-to-needle distance d used in the radius study.

The VME radius was swept over $r \in \{0.3, 0.5, 1.5, 2.5, 5\}$ mm with all other parameters held fixed. For each radius and σ_2 conditions, the conductivity of layer 1 was estimated from the simulated potentials using (15). The mean absolute error percentage (MAEP) was used to evaluate the accuracy of σ_1 via (19). The resulting MAEP values (Fig. 6) remained consistently low ($\sim 1.5\%$) across all radii and both conductivity contrasts, with no clear monotonic dependence on r being observed.

$$MAEP = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{\hat{y}_i - y_i}{y_i} \right| \times 100 \quad (19)$$

Furthermore, a one-way repeated-measures analysis of variance (ANOVA) across the five radii, using MAEP as the dependent variable, yielded $p = 0.4340 > 0.05$, indicating that the assumption that the electrode radius have a statistically significant effect on estimation accuracy could not be confirmed. Given the absence of a measurable accuracy benefit from larger electrodes and considering integration constraints for clinical use, $r = 0.3$ mm was selected as the preferred radius. This choice minimizes footprint and preserves procedural workspace without sacrificing proximity-estimation performance.

Fig. 6. VME-radius sweep and conductivity-estimation accuracy.

TABLE II
ESTIMATION ACCURACY ACROSS VME-PAIR POSITIONING PARAMETRIC STUDY

23-26	16-19	9-12		2-5		
4.72%/4.72%	2.85%/3.13%	2.03%/2.32%		1.18%/1.52%		
23-25	16-18	9-11		2-4		
3.44%/3.60%	2.28%/2.75%	1.79%/1.99%		1.16%/1.31%		
23-24	16-17	9-10		2-3		
1.79%/1.89%	1.28%/1.07%		1.01%/0.90%			
2.90%/3.03%	16-23	9-23	9-16	2-23	2-16	2-9
	1.81%/3.15%	1.91%/2.74%	1.79%/1.99%	1.75%/2.20%	1.22%/1.74%	1.26%/1.44%
23-27	16-20	9-13		2-6		
3.02%/3.20%	1.63%/2.09%	1.11%/1.17%		1.05%/1.13%		
23-28	16-21	9-14		2-7		
3.80%/3.60%	1.98%/2.78%	1.66%/1.65%		1.13%/1.40%		
23-29	16-22	9-15		2-8		
4.99%/4.31%	2.62%/3.30%	1.94%/2.18%		1.16%/1.59%		

B. Parametric Study: Electrode Positioning

The influence of the VME placement relative to the needle entry point was assessed with the electrode radius fixed to $r = 0.3$ mm (Sec. III-A). Candidate positions were arranged on the surface as shown in Fig. 7 ($X - Y$ view): the needle entry, inserted from 1 mm to 29 mm depth, is indexed as point 1. The investigated VME site are marked with indices 2–29. Two geometric attributes were systematically varied: (i) the relative orientation of each VME pair—*planar*, in which both electrodes lie along the same line through the entry point (e.g., pair 2–9), versus *orthogonal*, in which both electrodes are placed on a line orthogonal to a line that through the entry point (e.g., pair 2–3); (ii) the spatial offset from the entry point, obtained by selecting pairs at increasing inter-electrode distances (e.g., 2–23 vs. 2–9 and 2–5 vs. 2–3). A nominal spacing of 20 mm was retained to preserve space for the needle insertion operation.

Thirty VME-pair combinations were simulated in EIDORS, encompassing both orientation classes and a range of offsets. For each pair and for conductivity-contrast scenarios of $\sigma_2 = 0.1$ and 10 S/m, the conductivity of layer 1 was estimated via (15). Accuracy was quantified by the MAEP with respect to the ground truth σ_1 . The resulting MAEP field for the low-conductivity contrast ($\sigma_2 = 0.1$ S/m) is depicted as a color map in Fig.7. Table II lists all numerical performance metrics for both scenarios.

Two principal trends were identified. First, the estimation accuracy worsens as the VME pair is positioned farther from the entry site and as the inter-electrode separation widens;

Fig. 7. Error color map of parametric study on VME-pair spacing and placement.

Second, in the vicinity of the entry point, orthogonal configurations offer better accuracy than planar arrangements. Specifically, the orthogonal pair 2–3 achieved an MAEP approximately 20% lower than the planar pair 2–9 under both conductivity-contrast conditions (Table II).

C. Inclined Needle Insertion

When the needle is inclined by an angle θ relative to the surface normal (Fig. 8(a)), the orthogonal geometry remains feasible after substituting the projected distances

$$d' = |d - c \cdot \sin(\theta)|, \quad c' = |c \cdot \cos(\theta)| \quad (20)$$

into (15). By contrast, in the planar configuration, a geometric singularity arises when $|AM| = |AN|$ (Fig. 8(b)). Under this symmetry, Eq. (15) returns $\sigma_1 = 0$, which is non-physical. In the orthogonal layout, this degeneracy is excluded by geometry: the CSE A and VME M lie along the needle plane, whereas the other VME N is placed on the orthogonal axis, so $|AM| = |AN|$ will not be satisfied within any placements and insertion angles, and the singularity does not occur.

Given its higher accuracy and lack of singularities, the orthogonal layout was selected. Ultrasound-guided access guidance was used as the reference for the operating space [50]. Accordingly, the skin puncture was placed approximately one vessel depth from the target, and a 20 mm probe-to-needle gap was adopted.

D. Sensitivity Analysis

Using the optimal layout from the parametric study, the sensitivity of the proposed model was assessed in EIDORS by sweeping the layer-to-layer conductivity contrast, since the reflected component strengthens when the second layer is either far less or far more

Fig. 8. Inclined needle insertion. (a) With the orthogonal layout, needle insertions inclined by θ relative to the surface. (b) In the planar layout, symmetry can yield $|AM| = |AN|$, causing a geometric singularity.

conductive than the first. In EIDORS, the first layer was fixed at $\sigma_1 = 1$ S/m and varied the second layer over $\sigma_2 \in \{0.01, 0.02, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.5, 2, 5, 10, 20, 50, 100\}$ S/m, which yields contrast ratios (CR) $\sigma_1/\sigma_2 \in \{100, 50, 20, 10, 5, 2, 0.5, 0.2, 0.1, 0.05, 0.02, 0.01\}$. For each CR, σ_1 was estimated via (15), and sensitivity was quantified by the MAEP. Plotting MAEP against $\log(CR)$ (Fig. 9) shows a clear convergence trend: MAEP decreases as $|\log(CR)|$ increases, indicating higher accuracy under stronger contrast where the reflected component dominates. Even near $\log(CR) \approx 0$, where the layers are similar and sensitivity is most demanding, MAEP remains below 1.5%. These results indicate high sensitivity and accuracy across both low- and high-contrast regimes.

Fig. 9. Sensitivity analysis to layer conductivity contrast ratio.

E. Proximity Estimation in Layered Media

With the optimal VME radius and placement fixed, the proposed model was evaluated in EIDORS for layered tissue conditions, in which a two-layer medium was constructed (Fig.10(a)). The stimulating needle was modeled as a cylinder of radius 0.65 mm (Sec. III-A), consistent with the clinical needle. The layer 1 depth was set to $h = 30$ mm, representative of common tissue depth of needle-based interventions such as FAA and prostate biopsy. During the needle insertion simulation, the needle advanced toward the second layer with 1 mm increments while the impedance Z_{MN} between the VMEs M and N was recorded (Fig. 10(b)).

In Fig. 10(b), the simulated insertions show a monotonic decrease of Z_{MN} with increased insertion depth, consistent

Fig. 10. Proximity estimation in EIDORS layered media. (a) Two-layer FEM setup: upper $\sigma_1 = 1$ S/m, lower $\sigma_2 \in \{0.1, 10\}$ S/m, interface at $h = 30$ mm. (b) Z_{MN} decreases monotonically with insertion depth for both scenarios, absolute impedance is lower for $\sigma_2 = 10$ S/m, reflecting higher overall conductivity.

with (12) and (13). As the CSE electrode, which is the tip of the needle, moves farther away from the VMEs, the surface potentials V_M and V_N decrease, reducing the measured voltage difference and, consequently, the resulting impedance Z_{MN} . Another point to observe is that the absolute impedance is lower for $\sigma_2 = 10$ S/m than for $\sigma_2 = 0.1$ S/m, reflecting the higher tissue conductivity.

Proximity was then estimated through (18) with Z_{MN} , the geometric distances $|AM|$ and $|AN|$, and the reflected paths specified in Sec. II-C (16) and (17). At each insertion step, all unknown parameters in (18) were estimated simultaneously using MATLAB's gradient-based `fmincon` with bound constraints. Figure 11(a) summarizes the estimated h and σ_1 . Ground-truth references are shown as red dashed lines at $h = 30$ mm and $\sigma_1 = 1$ S/m. The estimated h for $\sigma_2 = 0.1$ S/m is shown as a blue solid curve, whereas the estimate for $\sigma_2 = 10$ S/m appears as a blue dashed curve and both closely follow the ground truth across the insertion. For conductivity, the estimates rendered as a green solid line for $\sigma_2 = 0.1$ S/m and a green dashed line for $\sigma_2 = 10$ S/m, again tracking the reference closely. Quantitatively, the depth errors were 0.55 mm root mean square error (RMSE) and 1.06 mm maximal absolute error (MAE) for $\sigma_2 = 0.1$ S/m, and 0.40 mm and 1.21 mm for $\sigma_2 = 10$ S/m. The conductivity estimates achieved a MAEP equals to 0.37% and 0.25% for $\sigma_2 = 0.1$ and 10 S/m, respectively.

The tip-interface proximity is provided in Fig. 11(b). The ground-truth proximity curve (red dashed) was obtained by subtracting the insertion depth from the ground truth $h = 30$ mm. The estimated proximity was formed identically using the estimated layer depth, yielding a blue solid line for $\sigma_2 = 0.1$ S/m and a blue dashed line for $\sigma_2 = 10$ S/m. Both estimated curves closely align with the ground truth throughout the whole traversal. Because proximity is computed from the depth estimate as proximity equals to $h - c$ with constant step size. Consequently, the proximity traces inherit the same RMSE and MAE as the h estimates, confirming millimeter accuracy and supporting the layered-medium framework.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION AND RESULTS

In this section, the proposed model was evaluated under benchtop conditions to corroborate the simulation findings and to assess performance in realistic environments. Validation proceeded in two stages. First, experiments in a saline solution were conducted to (i) confirm the electrode layout strategy

Fig. 11. Proximity and parameter estimation in layered media. (a) Depth h and conductivities σ_1 were estimated at 1 mm steps by fusing Z_{MN} with geometric distances. (b) Tip–interface proximity derived from estimated h tracks the ground-truth trajectory (red dashed) across 30 mm.

identified by EIDORS simulation and (ii) quantify proximity-distance estimation. Second, an *ex vivo* study using real tissue was performed to examine the model’s functioning in a biologically representative medium. To reflect the expected clinical use, both stages included insertions at multiple angles, enabling an assessment of proximity estimation under varying approach trajectories.

A. Experimental Setup

Figure 12(a) depicts the benchtop experiment setup, which is organized based on a saline tank (7). An electrical bio-impedance (EBI) spectroscopy (1) (Eliko Tehnoloogia Arenduskeskus, Estonia) is connected to two VMEs (6) and to the CSE. The CSE is provided by (1), an 18-gauge IV catheter needle (BD InsyteW®, USA) whose shaft is enclosed within its plastic sheath as the real clinical using case, so that only the distal tip remains exposed, thereby localizing current injection to the needle tip.

Fig. 12. Experimental setup: (1)–electrical bio-impedance spectroscopy device; (2)–multi-DOF stage; (3)–DC motor; (4)–motor controller; (5)–IV catheter; (6)–two VMEs; (7)–water tank; (8)–aluminum breadboard; (9)–motor power supply; (10)–NI® cRIO;

The needle was mounted on a linear actuator driven by a DC motor (3) (LM 2070-040-11, Faulhaber, Germany) under the control of a dedicated servo drive (4) (MC5005 S, Faulhaber, Germany), delivering a constant insertion velocity of 1 mm/s. Both the actuator and the VME holder were affixed to (2), a multi-degree-of-freedom positioning stage, enabling precise translational and rotational alignment and to prescribe different insertion angles.

All electrodes are immersed in a 0.2% saline bath contained within the tank. Four reference electrodes attached to the tank corners are tied to the electric ground, establishing a broad, uniform return path. Needle position and EBI data are synchronously sampled at 500 Hz via a NI® CompactRIO (10). The entire assembly is secured to an aluminum breadboard (8) to ensure mechanical rigidity, and a dedicated power supply (9). This provides a stable drive voltage to the motor.

B. Experiments in Saline Solution

A series of benchtop experiments were conducted in this conductive saline solution. Specifically, the tests (i) contrasted the performance of the two VME layouts, planar and orthogonal, and (ii) validated the fidelity of proximity estimation while the needle approached a target layer at various insertion angles.

Fig. 13. Saline solution setup for VMEs placement comparison. (a) Planar VMEs layout. (b) Orthogonal VMEs layout.

1) *Electrode layout evaluation experiments:* The saline-bath experiments first tested whether the orthogonal VME placement predicted by the EIDORS study (Sec. III-B) confers an accuracy advantage over the planar layout. Both layouts were realized on the benchtop setup (Fig. 13) with identical geometry: an inter-electrode spacing of $|MN| = 20$ mm and a 20 mm offset between the needle entry point and VME M .

Throughout each trial the needle advanced toward a plastic reference layer at a constant velocity of $v = 1$ mm/s. The EBI Z_{MN} was sampled by the EBI sensor, and the insertion depth c was determined from the DC motor encoder. Geometric

Fig. 14. Proximity distance estimation of insertion under various insertion angles. (a) Measured Z_{MN} at $\theta = 15^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ$ shows a rise-peak-fall profile from the non-monotonic tip-VME distance $|AM|$ variation. (b) With angle-dependent geometry, estimated tip-to-layer proximity (solid) tracks ground truth (dashed) at all angles. Larger θ shifts curves rightward due to longer axial travel.

factors required by (15), specifically, w_n, c_n and their primed counterparts—were computed using (16) and (17). These quantities served as inputs to the proximity solver (18), which was executed for every depth increment.

Fig. 15. Saline solution proximity estimations of planar and orthogonal VMEs layouts.

The Ground-truth proximity was obtained from two landmarks in Z_{MN} . As the tip crossed the saline surface, the differential signal Z_{MN} showed the first distinct transition, and a second distinct transition occurred when the tip first contacted the plastic surface. The encoder distance between these two landmarks gives the ground-truth layer depth h . At each insertion step, the ground-truth tip-to-target distance was then computed as $h - c$. This ground-truth proximity trace was plotted as the red dashed line in Fig. 15, alongside the model’s estimated tip-to-target distance. Figure 15 overlaid one of the estimated proximity for the planar (blue solid line) and orthogonal (green dash dot line) layouts. The orthogonal trace follows the ground truth more closely. Across five insertions, it reduces all error metrics (RMSE/MAE) at least by 20% versus the planar layout (Table III), confirming the electrode layout choice.

2) *Validation of proximity estimation under different insertion angles experiments:* In the real clinical settings, needle insertions are seldom strictly perpendicular to the tissue surface. Therefore, the experimental protocol was extended to oblique trajectories. With the multi-DOF stage (Fig. 16(a)), the catheter assembly was inclined by $0^\circ, 15^\circ, 30^\circ$, and 45° . For each angle, five insertions were executed at the same

Fig. 16. Oblique insertion in saline solution. (a) Benchtop setup for tilted insertion, $\theta = 15^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ$. (b) Geometry of tilted insertion: $|AM|$ decreases to a minimum and then increases.

speed with 1 mm/s. Ground-truth proximity was obtained as described in Sec. IV-B1).

Oblique insertions introduce an additional geometric relation between the needle axis and the VMEs. Figure 16(b) highlights this effect: as the needle is inclined by an angle θ , the tip-to-VME M distance $|AM|$ first shortens, reaches a minimum, then lengthens along the path. Since the impedance are inversely related to source-electrode separation based on the fundamental model in (12) and (13), this non-monotonic geometry yields a local maximum in the measured Z_{MN} (Fig. 14(a)). Each trace first rises while $|AM|$ decreased, and reaches the Z_{MN} peak at the geometric minimum, and then decreases as the insertion depth grows. Note that the larger insertion angle also alters the correspondence between the true layer depth h and the traveled distance c . For a fixed h , a large θ requires a longer path along the needle axis to reach the interface, hence the rightward shift of the curves in Fig. 14(b).

Angle-dependent geometry can then be accounted for by replacing the nominal separation terms with the projections defined in (20). The resulting Z_{MN} measurements and modified geometric factors were filled in (18) to yield tip-to-layer estimates. Table III summarizes the performance. Across all three different metrics (RMSE, MAE, Normalized Root Mean Square Error (NRMSE)), the orthogonal VMEs layout main-

TABLE III
PROXIMITY ESTIMATION RESULTS OF SALINE SOLUTION EXPERIMENTS
UNDER VARIOUS INSERTION ANGLES

Metrics	Layout	Planar		Orthogonal							
				0°		15°		30°		45°	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
RMSE (mm)		1.13	0.05	0.80	0.02	0.79	0.05	0.78	0.04	0.79	0.03
MAE (mm)		1.67	0.12	1.36	0.17	1.10	0.08	1.20	0.10	1.10	0.07
NRMSE (%)		3.00	0.14	2.11	0.05	2.04	0.10	1.79	0.14	1.36	0.06

tains millimeter accuracy. The correspondingly small standard deviations ($SD < 0.1$ mm) indicate high repeatability over the five trials at each angle. These results confirm that the proposed model, augmented with the angle-corrected geometry, maintains robust proximity estimation under clinically relevant insertion angles.

C. Ex Vivo Experiments

To extend validation beyond saline phantoms, *ex vivo* trials were conducted to examine (i) the homogeneous-tissue characterization model of Sec. II-B and (ii) the layered-tissue proximity model of Sec. II-C. Two successive stages were performed: first, needle insertions into single-tissue blocks were used to estimate bulk conductivity; second, insertions into layered tissue were made to evaluate proximity estimation at oblique angles.

Fig. 17. *Ex vivo* setup for characterizing two tissue types. (a) Porcine muscle (higher conductivity). (b) Porcine fat (lower conductivity).

1) *Tissue characterization experiments*: Blocks of porcine muscle (higher water/ion content) and fat (lower water content) served as representative high- and low-conductivity tissues (Fig. 17). The orthogonal VME arrangement was retained, with $|MN| = 20$ mm and a 20 mm offset between the needle entry point and VME M . Four self-adhesive ECG electrodes (Kendall®, Covidien, Ireland) provided a distributed electric ground to ensure a locally uniform electrical field.

The IV catheter needle, acting as the CSE, advanced into the tissue at 1 mm/s. Z_{MN} was recorded continuously, while insertion depth c was obtained from the motor encoder. Geometric factors $|AM|$ and $|AN|$ were calculated via Eq. (11) and, together with Z_{MN} , supplied to Eq. (10) to yield the tissue-specific electrical conductivity σ_1 .

Five insertions were performed at spatially distinct sites on each tissue block. Figure 18 aggregates the resulting σ_1 profiles. The five repetitions clustered tightly - $SD = 0.006$ S/m for muscle and $SD = 0.007$ S/m for fat - indicating high

Fig. 18. *Ex vivo* tissue conductivity estimations in homogeneous tissues. Shaded bands indicate literature-reported conductivity ranges for muscle (green) and fat (red) [48].

Fig. 19. Layered *ex vivo* tissue setup with $\theta = 0^\circ, 15^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ$.

repeatability. In addition, the estimated values range in the reported literature ($0.3\text{--}0.7$ S/m for muscle and $0.01\text{--}0.1$ S/m for fat [48]), demonstrating the precision of the homogeneous tissue model and providing a solid foundation for subsequent proximity studies.

2) *Ex vivo layered tissue proximity estimation experiments*: A layered porcine specimen containing an fat layer over muscle was mounted beneath the orthogonal layout (Fig. 19). The catheter needle was oriented at four clinically relevant angles, $\theta = 0^\circ, 15^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ$, using the rotation stage, and five insertions were performed under each inclination.

Figure 20(a) plots the raw Z_{MN} signals acquired during insertions at the four different angles. The absolute impedance level differs significantly from one angle to another. This disparity arises because each inclination forces the needle to enter the specimen at a distinct surface location and to traverse a unique three-dimensional path through the fat layer before reaching muscle. Consequently, the current pathways vary across angles and so do the measured impedance. While the needle tip moves within the fat layer, the impedance-depth curve maintains an almost smooth curve trend. When the tip reaches the fat-muscle interface, that curve changes abruptly because muscle has a markedly different conductivity (Fig. 21). The insertion distance between the (i) first contact with the fat surface and (ii) the point of this sudden change gives the true fat-layer depth h . Figure 20(b) overlays the

Fig. 20. Layered *ex vivo* proximity distance estimation results at $\theta = 0^\circ, 15^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ$. (a) Absolute EBI Z_{MN} levels differ by angle due to distinct entry points and insertion path through fat before reaching muscle. (b) Estimated tip-to-layer proximity (solid) closely follows ground truth (dashed) for all angles. Larger angle θ shifts the curves rightward due to the longer axial travel. (c) Impedance changes abruptly at the fat-muscle interface.

Fig. 21. Impedance changes abruptly at the fat-muscle interface.

TABLE IV
PROXIMITY ESTIMATION RESULTS OF *Ex vivo* EXPERIMENTS UNDER VARIOUS INSERTION ANGLES

Metrics	Layout		0°		15°		30°		45°	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
RMSE (mm)	1.00	0.07	1.13	0.04	1.13	0.03	1.11	0.03	1.11	0.03
MAE (mm)	1.30	0.05	1.58	0.06	1.51	0.10	1.48	0.08	1.48	0.08
NRMSE (%)	4.74	0.14	4.71	0.29	3.86	0.08	3.43	0.06	3.43	0.06

resulting proximity estimates on their ground truth. Across all angles, the estimator tracks the reference closely, and the slight rightward shift of the curves at larger θ reflects the longer axial travel required to reach the same anatomical interface.

Table IV summaries performance across the five repetitions per angle. The RMSE ranges from 1.00 mm to 1.13 mm, MAE ranges from 1.30 to 1.58 mm, and normalized RMSE remains below 4.8%. Standard deviations are low (≤ 0.1 mm), reflecting the high repeatability of the measurements across the five insertions at each angle. Although errors are slightly higher than in saline due to tissue heterogeneity and surface compliance, the results confirm that the angle-corrected model delivers millimeter proximity estimation in *ex vivo* biological tissue under clinically realistic oblique trajectories.

V. DISCUSSION

This study validated a physics-based EBI model in successive steps, beginning with homogeneous media for tissue characterization and subsequently extending to a two-layer

configuration for proximity estimation. The single-layer formulation—first confirmed numerically in EIDORS and then corroborated in saline as well as *ex vivo* muscle and fat, forms the analytical basis for more complex layers. Although only two layers were examined, the reflection logic in Sec. II-C could be generalized to multiple interfaces. Therefore, clinical scenarios involving three or more anatomical layers could be accommodated by iteratively cascading the proposed model without modifying the core framework.

Earlier tripolar-impedance work demonstrated that surface scans can estimate the depth of a subsurface boundary prior to puncture [51]. The present study extends that concept by incorporating the advancing needle itself as the CSE, thereby enabling continuous, step-wise estimation of the tip-to-interface distance throughout the insertion. This progression from pre-puncture depth sensing to real-time intra-tissue tracking represents a substantive advance, particularly for high-risk procedures in which every millimeter of needle travel is clinically consequential.

When contrasted with mainstream sensing technologies, the proposed EBI sensing-based strategy offers complementary strengths. Ultrasound provides real-time visualization but its axial resolution and susceptibility to acoustic shadowing limit its ability to localize the fine needle, especially the needle tip relative to a thin plane. Fluoroscopy achieves higher spatial resolution yet entails ionizing radiation and substantial capital cost. The EBI approach is radiation-free. It requires only inexpensive surface electrodes, and delivers a numerical estimate of tip-to-layer separation with millimeter accuracy, even along oblique trajectories that can confound image-based depth perception. Accordingly, it can function either as a stand-alone metric in low-resource settings or as a quantitative adjunct to imaging when maximal spatial certainty is required.

Progressive increases in estimation error were observed when moving from simulation to saline and finally to biological tissue (Sec. III-E, Table III, Table IV). Two factors dominate this trend. First, real tissue exhibits local conductivity heterogeneity that violates the homogeneity assumption underlying the FEM model and perturb the ideal electrical field. Second, mechanical effects, due to needle deflection and tissue deformation, alter the geometry terms and modulate the impedance signal, whereas such effects are absent in

simulation and negligible in saline. A small early deviation from ground truth is also visible in Fig. 14(b) and Fig. 20(b). When the needle tip CSE is far from the target layer, current density is low by Eq. (1), the signal is weaker, and estimates are less accurate. As the tip approaches the interface, current density rises, the impedance signal strengthens, and accuracy improves toward the end of insertion. Despite these challenges, the algorithm maintained millimeter range RMSE and MAE, with standard deviations below 0.10 mm, demonstrating robust and repeatable performance.

The proposed model accuracy is inherently tied to geometric fidelity. A comprehensive parametric sweep identified an orthogonal VME layout as optimal, simultaneously avoiding model singularities and minimizing error. Nevertheless, reliable knowledge of the inter-electrode gap s , the offset d between VME M and the needle entry point, the insertion depth c , and the approach angle θ remains essential. A promising avenue for future work could be the development of an integrated “geometry-locking” kit: a disposable fixture that locks the VME pair into the prescribed orthogonal arrangement, provides a dedicated guide hole for the needle, and encodes s and d by design. When this kit is integrated with a robotically actuated insertion stage governed by the proposed real-time EBI proximity estimator, the needle depth c can be regulated with millimeter precision, preserving the model’s geometric assumptions while adding only modest complexity to the clinical workflow.

VI. CONCLUSION

This work proposed a physic-based EBI model with millimeter proximity accuracy under a spectrum of FEM simulation, saline phantoms, and layered *ex vivo* tissue—while consistently delivering repeatable conductivity estimates in layered-medium. Together, these results establish a robust foundation for EBI sensing-based guidance in anatomically complex settings. By mapping EBI measurements to an estimate of the interface depth and combining this with the measured insertion depth, the proposed model provides the quantitative tip-to-interface distance required for informed clinical decision-making. Furthermore, this framework is intrinsically tool-agnostic and readily extendable to multi-layer anatomies, offering a general EBI sensing-based solution adaptable to diverse clinical scenarios. Future efforts will integrate multi-layer extensions into real-time clinical prototypes and quantify the influence of physiological motion and perfusion on estimation fidelity.

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